

Deep learning for the detection of colon polyps with malignant potential: ex vivo classification using feature-enhanced optical coherence tomography (OCT) images

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Abstract: Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the second leading cause of cancer-related morbidity and mortality in both men and women globally. CRC predominantly arises from dysplastic polyps that, over time, progressively evolve into malignancies. Population-wide screening through colonoscopy remains the cornerstone of CRC prevention. Optical coherence tomography (OCT) has the potential to increase the effectiveness and reduce the cost associated with colonoscopic screening. However, conclusive evidence that OCT can effectively detect pre-cancerous changes is still lacking. This study introduces a novel framework to address this challenge by extracting additional features, which can serve as biomarkers of disease, from ex vivo OCT images of colon polyps. These include first and second-order intensity and fractal statistics, as well as spectral characteristics and scatterer size, which depend on sub-cellular and biochemical tissue variations. Feature-enhanced images derived from these biomarkers were combined with intensity images and integrated into a deep-learning classification model decision-level fusion. This approach achieved 88.3% accuracy, 93.5% sensitivity, 77.9% specificity, and an AUC of 0.857 in distinguishing benign (normal and hyperplastic) polyps from cases with malignant potential (adenoma and sessile serrated adenoma), demonstrating the potential of this novel approach to enhance the role of OCT in improving CRC screening outcomes.

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1. Introduction

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is a leading cause of cancer deaths, with more than 400,000 new cases in 2024 in Europe [1]. In the USA, approximately 150,000 new cases are expected in 2024 [2]. CRCs mainly develop from polyps or adenomas with dysplasia. Over time, polyps gradually evolve into malignancies. Therefore, population-based screening, for the examination of suspicious lesions, is both a viable and an important cancer prevention strategy. It is estimated that screening has the potential to reduce the burden of CRC, with a decrease in mortality ranging from 18% to 57% [3]. Since 2003, the European Council proposed the implementation of CRC screening for men and women aged 50 - 74 year [4]. Sedated colonoscopy accounts for most of CRC screening procedures, contributing to a 35% decline in overall CRC mortality over the past two decades [5]. However, many adults do not adhere to the standard screening recommendations. In addition, the rate of CRC incidence has increased by 8% over the last decade, increasing the number of colonoscopies required [2]. Although colonoscopy is an effective screening technique, there is room for improvement. Colonoscopy misses 20-30% of adenomas due to (i) inadequate sampling using the forward viewing endoscope that misses polyps behind the colon's folds [6,7], and flat serrated lesions [8], (ii) inadequate time and care spent inspecting the mucosa [6,8] and

(iii) lack of real time feedback due to the need for further histological processing. Non-detected lesions lead to cancers that arise in between colonoscopic screenings, accounting for about 10% of new cases [9]. New endoscopic technology, which meets field-specific performance thresholds, can reduce procedure time, pathology burden, and cost by leaving diminutive polyps (<5 mm) in place [10]. However, such a strategy introduces additional risks since it implies leaving 80% of the now-resected, polyps in place. Hence, along with increased vigilance, advancements in technology are required to ensure that polyps which carry malignant potential are detected with high sensitivity, and resected.

Novel imaging approaches have been proposed to improve the efficacy of colonoscopy. For example, narrow-band imaging (NBI) can increase the contrast between polyps, colorectal cancer, and normal background tissue. NBI has limits, and polyps do not always clearly stand out from the background mucosa [11,12]. Detecting and classifying polyps can be addressed with Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT). OCT can rapidly and non-invasively generate three-dimensional (3D) images of tissue microstructure at a resolution of 10-20 μm , in the case of viable *in vivo* clinical system. This technology has been explored as a means for optical biopsy since early in its development. However, OCT imaging in the colon has not advanced as much as other clinical applications since, until recently, there were no endoscopic OCT systems to comprehensively image the large diameter and corrugated anatomy of this organ [13]. Even with recent system developments [14,15], the diagnostic accuracy of OCT for pre-cancerous colon polyps is not well-established. One of the reasons is that relying solely on structural information has limits. Thus far, the diagnosis is based on the OCT images of tissue microstructure and heuristic “radiological-like” criteria, without the sub-cellular, functional or biochemical information required to identify early signs of malignant transformation, including dysplasia [16].

To circumvent the limitations of attempting a diagnosis based solely on tissue architecture further analysis was performed of the OCT data. The analysis includes statistical intensity features and texture-based characteristics of the OCT images [17,18]. Recently, other characteristics that can also serve as biomarkers of disease were also extracted from OCT data. These novel features included scatterer size, which mainly depends on the size of the nuclei of the cells, and group velocity dispersion and refractive index, which depend on sub-cellular biochemical alterations caused by disease [19–24]. Spectroscopic OCT (SOCT) was also applied in a study focused on detecting cancer progression in the azoxymethane rat carcinogenesis model and in a small dataset of *ex vivo* human polyps [25,26]. This application involved analyzing the tissue’s optical properties and quantifying the size of the cell nucleus at various tissue depths. Another technique, inverse spectroscopic OCT (ISOCT), employed a robust scattering model to derive the optical properties from SOCT data [27,28]. ISOCT was successfully used to distinguish advanced adenomas in colorectal epithelium from biopsy samples. Zhu, et al, demonstrated that the colorectal epithelium could also be assessed using scattering coefficient maps [29], an optical property measurable via OCT.

Neural networks to automate the diagnosis based on OCT images of colorectal specimens were also developed. Zeng et al. Applied the RetinaNet pattern recognition model to OCT B-Scan images acquired with a benchtop OCT system [30], achieving 100% sensitivity and 99% specificity in distinguishing normal from malignant colorectal specimens. Similarly, Luo et al. designed a miniaturized OCT catheter integrated with a ResNet deep neural network to acquire and classify, in real-time, endoluminal OCT images as normal or malignant, achieving an accuracy of 92.9% and an area under the ROC curve (AUC) of 0.975 [31]. Furthermore, Nie et al., investigated the feasibility of using an endoscopic OCT catheter for *in vivo* complex polyp assessment during colonoscopy. They trained a vision transformer (ViT) model to differentiate benign from deeply invasive lesions in real time. The study, which included 35 polyps from 32 patients, demonstrated an accuracy of 95% and an AUC of 0.984 [32].

A common limitation of most of the previous studies is their focus on detecting advanced CRC. However, this is not adequate in *leave-in-situ* management schemes since the decision to resect or not is based on the presence of dysplasia, an early pre-cancerous condition. In this study, the focus is to differentiate non-malignant samples, including hyperplastic polyps and normal tissue, deemed suspicious and extracted during endoscopy, from lesions with malignant potential, i.e. adenomas and sessile serrated adenomas (SSA). This level of differentiation is essential for the implementation of *leave-in-situ* polyp management strategies. *Ex vivo* OCT images of human polyps, from patients undergoing colonoscopy, were acquired and processed using a fully automated algorithm for image segmentation and feature extraction. Features included first and second order intensity and fractal statistics as well as spectral characteristics. Feature-enhanced OCT images were created by overlaying the values of the most significant features as a color scale onto the intensity OCT images. These enhanced images were utilized in a novel deep learning model, incorporating decision-level fusion, to distinguish benign (normal and hyperplastic) from malignant-potential (adenoma and SSA) polyps.

2. Theory and methods

2.1. Dataset

The OCT data for this project were collected using a Fourier Domain OCT system, with a center wavelength of 1310 nm, an axial resolution of 14 μm , and an A-Scan rate of 100 kHz. The OCT performance was calibrated periodically using a mirror. The data was collected at the Massachusetts General Hospital after internal review board (IRB) approval. Informed consent was obtained prior to the procedure. The imaging took place in the colonoscopy suite immediately after the resection of each polyp. Subsequently, histological H&E sections and diagnosis were also provided. *En face* images were used to outline the extent of the polyp in the imaging volume as well as areas of histology-confirmed diagnosis (normal, hyperplastic, adenoma, SSA) to be used as the ground truth. Polyps were intercepted from 135 subjects and imaged prior to standard-of-care histological processing. Scans from 18 of those patients were excluded for inadequate signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), image quality (e.g. focusing), or tissue artifacts (e.g. fecal contents). The remaining data set ($N = 117$) was annotated by an expert histopathologist (Fig. 1(A)) using the pathology core diagnosis. 69 polyps were labeled as benign (normal and hyperplastic), and 72 polyps as having malignant-potential (adenoma and SSA).

2.2. Image processing and feature extraction

Each B-Scan image that was assigned a diagnosis by the expert histopathologist was automatically segmented to retrieve the top portion of the colon image (Fig. 1(B)). Segmentation was performed by thresholding, followed by a series of morphological operations to remove small regions due to noise and vertical and horizontal lines caused by bright specular reflections. The top surface was identified and the section between the top surface and 150 μm below was segmented (Fig. 1(C)). Various features were derived from the neighborhoods of each image, belonging to the following categories:

- (i) **Intensity Statistics (First Order):** Several first-order intensity measures were computed for each neighborhood within the segmented image regions. These included metrics such as the mean, standard deviation, variance, skewness, median, kurtosis, minimum, mode, and maximum intensity values. These descriptors capture crucial textural properties.
- (ii) **Intensity Statistics (Second Order):** The perceptual texture qualities of the images were evaluated using the Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM). Four primary attributes - correlation, contrast, homogeneity, and energy - were extracted. The correlation coefficient reflects the relationship between two pixels; a high value indicates similar pixel intensities,

Fig. 1. (A) An *en face* projection of a polyp created from a volume of 1000 OCT images (each 1000 A-Scans \times 1024 pixels). The yellow line marks the extend of the polyp. The green and red lines indicate normal and adenomatous sections of the polyp as marked by an expert pathologist. (B) The section of the OCT image, corresponding to the green dashed line in A. The green lines demarcate the automatically segmented surface and a depth of 150 μm below. (C) The section of the image between the green lines in B.

while a low value suggests dissimilar ones. Contrast measures the intensity difference between neighboring pixels, with high contrast indicating large variations and low contrast indicating minimal differences. Homogeneity assesses the uniformity of adjacent pixel values; high homogeneity implies similar neighboring values, while low homogeneity suggests diverse values. Energy quantifies uniformity within the region, where higher energy indicates a more consistent intensity distribution. GLCM features were computed in four orientations (0° , 45° , 90° , and 135°) and at three different offsets (1, 3, and 5 pixels) relative to the neighborhood center.

- (iii) **Fractals (Fractal Dimension):** The fractal dimension (FD) serves as a metric for assessing the complexity and irregularity of image structures, making it particularly useful in medical imaging to identify irregularities commonly associated with diseases. The box-counting method was employed to calculate the statistical distribution of FD across all neighborhoods of each image [33].
- (iv) **Spectral Features:** Beyond the intensity data used for generating micro-structural images, OCT interferograms provide spectral information. According to Mie scattering theory, oscillatory spectral patterns correspond to scatterer size. To estimate the average scatterer size, primarily influenced by the nuclei of cells *in situ*, a novel metric called the correlation of the derivative (COD) bandwidth was applied [22]. Briefly, the width of the autocorrelation of the derivative of the OCT spectrum, provides a measure of the periodicity of the spectral variations caused by discrete scatterers as predicted by Mie theory. Furthermore, narrowband spectral intensities and their ratios were computed for 3, 5, 7, and 15 spectral bands spanning the full spectrum

For the purposes of this study, each feature was estimated within an 11×11 pixel neighborhood ($55 \times 55 \mu\text{m}$). Various neighborhood sizes were evaluated and the optimal size for classification was selected. First and second order intensity and fractal features were calculated for both logarithmic and non-logarithmic intensity images. The feature values were overlaid over the intensity OCT image as a color value in an HSV image, where hue (H) represented the value of the feature and value (V) was set to the intensity of the OCT structural image. The saturation (S)

was set to 1 everywhere (Fig. 2). All the images were normalized to the same color range to ensure good contrast and make the results comparable and converted to RGB format.

Fig. 2. Examples of images of (A) normal, (B) hyperplastic, (C) adenomatous, and (D) SSA polyps, and feature-enhanced images using the median of the fractal dimension in a non-log image (column 2), the mean of the intensity in the log image (column 3), and the COD bandwidth of the spectrum (column 4). The color bar represents the HSV color variation of the normalized feature images (0: min value – 1: max value).

2.3. Deep learning classification with decision-level fusion using intensity images

The effectiveness of the feature-based OCT image enhancement was evaluated. To serve as a baseline, intensity images alone were first classified. Grayscale and pseudo-color images were extracted from the annotated sections of the OCT volumes. Pseudocolor images were included to investigate whether details enhanced by color coding could improve the classification of the intensity images. They were generated by replacing the grayscale intensity value with the color defined in a lookup table (“jet” colormap). Although, an optimal colormap for classification may exist, this was not further investigated here. Each annotated region was divided into 127 A-Scan sections and converted into 127×127 -pixel ($650 \times 150 \mu\text{m}$) images for deep learning. Figure 3 shows some representative intensity images of polyps with different histopathologic diagnosis. The images are displayed with a normalized logarithmic intensity scale.

The intensity images were classified in two classes, benign (normal and hyperplastic) vs. malignant-potential (adenoma and SSA) using a ResNet18 network. A total of 8 different datasets were created using intensity images with different pre-processing steps. The datasets included normalized / not normalized intensity, logarithmic scale / linear scale, and grayscale / pseudocolor. Each dataset consisted of 10409 images from 117 patients. Data augmentation was implemented by applying a set of operations to the original images during training. The operations included rotations as well as translations in the x and y scale for each image. After comparing the classification results and computation times of various pre-trained networks in MATLAB, including GoogLeNet, ResNet-101, Inception, and ShuffleNet, ResNet-18 was chosen as it demonstrated the best and fastest performance. The ResNet18 network was pretrained with the ImageNet dataset. Its last layers were modified to incorporate a fully connected layer

Fig. 3. Examples intensity images of (A) normal, (B) hyperplastic, (C) adenomatous, and (D) SSA polyps, in normalized logarithmic grayscale (left) and pseudocolor (right) color schemes. The dimensions of the images are 127×127 pixels ($650 \times 150 \mu\text{m}$). The color bar represents the jet map color variation of the normalized feature images (0: min value – 1: max value)

for a two-class model, followed by a “Softmax” activation, and finally the classification layer. The Adam optimizer was used with a batch size of 128. The learning rate was set to 0.0001 and the network was trained with a validation frequency of 50 and a validation patience of 4 rounds. Each of the 8 datasets of images was classified using a separately trained network and a leave-ten-patient-out (L-10-PO) cross-validation testing scheme. Finally, decision-level fusion was performed to retrieve a single classification for each image. The scores from the output of the classification layer of each network (2 values) and their ratios were used to create a new feature vector for each image. A conventional linear discriminant analysis (LDA) classifier was applied to produce the final classification of each image (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Classification flow of the proposed deep learning model with decision-level fusion. Each image dataset passes through a separate ResNet18 neural network, and the scores are combined into a feature vector which is then used as the input to a traditional machine learning classifier (LDA) to produce a final classification for image.

2.4. Deep learning classification using feature-enhanced images with decision-level fusion

First, the extracted features, from individual neighborhoods, were ranked using 3 different ranking methods: minimum redundancy-maximum relevance (MRMR), Chi Square, and t-test and an overall ranking was calculated for each feature by averaging the ranking order from the three methods. In this process, only values from high intensity regions were included since those

correspond to the areas of epithelium. Enhanced OCT images were created using the values of the top-ranking features in each category. The number of features used was selected by successively adding more features until the algorithm's performance reached a plateau. An exhaustive evaluation of all possible combinations of features was not performed due to the time constraints imposed by the training of each network. The images were classified as benign (normal and hyperplastic) vs. malignant potential (adenoma and SSA). Data augmentation was implemented by applying a set of augmentation operations (i.e., translation and rotation) to the original images during training, as before. The same type of pre-trained ResNet18 neural network was utilized. Each dataset of feature-enhanced images was classified using a separately trained network with a leave-ten-patients-out (L10PO) cross-validation testing scheme. As before, decision-level fusion was performed to retrieve a single classification for each image. The scores from the output of the classification layer of each network (2 values) and their ratios were used to create a new feature vector for each image. A conventional linear discriminant analysis (LDA) classifier was applied to produce the final classification of each image (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Classification flow of the proposed multi-featured deep learning model with decision-level fusion. Each feature dataset passes through a separate ResNet18 neural network, and the scores are combined into a feature vector which is then used as the input to a traditional machine learning classifier (LDA) to produce a final classification of each image.

3. Results

The standard intensity and pseudocolor images were initially classified to serve as a baseline reference. The 8 image datasets were fed into separate ResNet-18 networks. Normalized logarithmic grayscale images provided the best classification performance, with 85.5% classification accuracy, 88.4% sensitivity, and 79.6% specificity (Table 1). The late fusion procedure of all the grayscale and pseudocolor deep learning scores improved the classification results to 87.3% classification accuracy, 91.9% sensitivity, 78.3% specificity, and an AUC of 0.851 (Fig. 6).

Feature-enhanced OCT images were created from the twenty-one most significant features selected. Those included: six first order intensity statistics, six GLCM features, four fractal statistics and five spectral features listed in order of significance per category in Table 2. The images were, initially, classified separately, resulting in accuracy ranging from 79.2% to 83.4%, sensitivity from 82.9% to 88.1%, and specificity from 65.8% to 76.0%. After decision-level fusion of the score vectors from the initial intensity datasets and the feature-enhanced OCT images, the performance improved, resulting in 88.3% accuracy, 93.5% sensitivity, 77.9% specificity, and an AUC of 0.857 (Fig. 7).

Table 1. Classification results using intensity and pseudocolor images.

Dataset	Accuracy (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	AUC
Grayscale No Norm and No Log	83.7	87.6	75.9	0.814
Grayscale Norm but No Log	84.8	87.9	78.5	0.832
Grayscale No Norm but Log	82.2	87.0	72.6	0.822
Grayscale Norm and Log	85.5	88.4	79.6	0.855
Pseudocolor No Norm and No Log	80.9	85.1	72.5	0.788
Pseudocolor Norm but No Log	84.3	88.5	76.0	0.822
Pseudocolor No Norm but Log	81.0	85.8	71.4	0.786
Pseudocolor Norm and Log	83.2	86.0	77.6	0.812

Fig. 7. ROC curve (AUC 0.857) and confusion matrix of decision-level fusion classification of benign vs. malignant-potential images using both feature-enhanced and intensity images.

Table 2. Classification results of the feature-enhanced images.

Dataset	Accuracy (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	AUC
Fractal Statistics of Normalized Logarithmic Images				
Variance (FD) ^a	80.7	84.8	72.5	0.787
Mean (FD)	81.5	85.9	72.7	0.792
Fractal Statistics of Normalized Non-Logarithmic Images				
Median (FD)	80.9	85.3	72.3	0.788
Mean (FD)	81.4	84.1	76.0	0.800
GLCM Features of Normalized Logarithmic Image				
Correlation - [-3 0] ^b	79.9	84.9	69.9	0.774
Contrast - [-3 0]	79.6	84.4	69.9	0.771
GLCM Features of Normalized Non-Logarithmic Images				
Correlation - [-3 0]	79.4	82.9	72.5	0.777
Contrast - [-3 3]	82.7	87.1	74.0	0.805
Average Homogeneity - [3] ^c	82.7	86.8	74.6	0.807
Average Correlation - [5]	81.5	85.9	72.9	0.793
Intensity Statistics of Normalized Logarithmic Images				
Variance (Intensity)	83.4	88.1	74.1	0.811
Mean (Intensity)	83.1	87.0	75.2	0.811
Intensity Statistics of Normalized Non-Logarithmic Images				
Median (Intensity)	83.4	87.8	74.8	0.813
Skewness (Intensity)	82.4	87.8	71.5	0.797
Mode (Intensity)	81.6	84.9	74.9	0.799
Min (Intensity)	81.9	85.9	73.8	0.798
Spectral Features of Normalized Images				
B1 of 15 / B10 of 15 ^d	79.5	85.0	68.4	0.767
B1 of 7 / B3 of 7	80.7	86.3	69.6	0.779
B1 of 3 / B3 of 3	80.3	85.2	70.4	0.778
COD ^e	83.0	85.8	77.5	0.816
B5 of 15 / B9 of 15	79.2	85.9	65.8	0.758

^aFD is the Fractal Dimension

^bThe numbers in the brackets are the distances, in pixels, [distance in x, distance in y], with respect to the center of the neighborhood.

^cThe number in the brackets is the distance, in pixels in all directions.

^d“Bn of N” denotes the total intensity of band n when the spectrum is divided into N bands

^eCOD is the bandwidth of the correlation of the derivative.

4. Discussion

This study utilizes deep learning and decision-level fusion to classify OCT colon polyp images into benign (normal and hyperplastic) vs. malignant potential (adenoma and SSA) categories. Using only the intensity information of the OCT images, this approach provided 87.3% classification accuracy, 91.9% sensitivity, 78.3% specificity, and an AUC of 0.851. Including images enhanced by incorporating various structural and spectral features, in the form of an HSV color scale, improved the classification to 88.3% accuracy, 93.5% sensitivity, 77.9% specificity, and an AUC of 0.857. The improvement in accuracy was statistically significant as assessed with a p-value of 0.007 [34]. The AUC change from 0.851 and 0.857 was also statistically significant based on the Delong, et al, method ($p = 0.009$). [35].

The number of patients included in this work, although larger than most of the previous studies, is still not large enough to confidently provide broad generalization of the results, especially since deep learning is involved. To mitigate this problem, transfer learning, in the form of pretraining the models, and basic augmentation was used. In addition, the dataset was not balanced (6931 malignant potential vs. 3478 benign images). However, these numbers represent the real-world occurrence of histopathologic diagnoses since the samples were not preselected based on stage. Both issues are best mitigated by the collection of additional images, which are currently being collected. Another limitation of this study is that the feature selection was performed with a combination of feature ranking, considering all the neighborhoods in an image, and manually testing the classification performance. Neither of the two steps is optimal. An exhaustive evaluation of the effect of all available feature combinations on the classification performance was also not performed. Unfortunately, such an endeavor is not practical given the amount of time required to train and test the deep learning models.

The analysis performed was limited to a tissue depth where the villi were still visible in the OCT images. Unfortunately, this is a fundamental limitation that could potentially lead to missing deeper changes. In addition, features from neighborhoods in the stroma of the tissue instead of the epithelium were not included in the feature ranking process given that the focus of the study was to detect early cancer changes. However, features from the stroma could be useful in the identification of invasion. In this work, only values from areas of high intensity, roughly corresponding to the epithelium, were considered. In the future, more sophisticated segmentation may result in a better selection of features.

5. Conclusions

In this study we have demonstrated that the combination of feature-enhanced OCT images and deep learning with decision-level fusion can provide improved classification performance between benign (normal and hyperplastic) vs. malignant potential (adenoma and SSA) B-Scan OCT images.

While studies using OCT images and deep learning models have achieved impressive results in distinguishing benign from invasive lesions or advanced cancerous polyps, that undertaking is significantly simplified by the visible differences the microstructure images. Furthermore, the few studies of precancerous lesions were limited to a small number of patients and did not include the necessary histological variability to adequately represent real world situations. Luo et al, proposed a customized ResNet for the classification of normal vs. colorectal cancer OCT images from 43 patients. The study reported an AUC of 0.975 but did not include any pre-cancerous lesions [31]. Zeng et al, utilized data from 33 patients to perform two classification tasks: normal vs. abnormal tissue, achieving 94.7% sensitivity and 94.0% specificity, and adenomatous polyp vs. cancerous tissue, with 86.9% sensitivity and 85.0% specificity. However, the dataset was limited to just four adenomatous samples and no hyperplastic tissue or serrated adenomas. In addition, the study employed random train-test partitioning without accounting for patient-level

data separation, potentially introducing data leakage between the training and testing sets. This methodological limitation raises concerns about assessment bias, as regions of interest (ROIs) from individual patients could be included in both sets, degrading data independence in model validation [29]. The same group utilized a RetinaNet-based system to distinguish normal from neoplastic tissue. Although this approach achieved 0.998 AUC, only two adenomatous polyps and no hyperplastic tissue were included in the study [30]. Nie et al, compared malignant-potential polyps (adenomas and SSAs), which they identified as “benign”, vs. cancer. That study examined 35 polyps from 32 patients, which, however, did not include any normal or hyperplastic tissue [32]. A recent study, by Kendall et al, compared OCT images of normal colon epithelium with adenomatous polyps and resulted in ~98% accuracy [26]. That work was also limited to a small number of patients, 18 in total, and lacked histological variability since it included no serrated lesions or benign hyperplastic polyps. In contrast, the proposed approach was applied to an image dataset from a larger number of patients and included samples from a wider range of pre-cancerous polyp types. This nuanced classification significantly increases the complexity of the task. With 93.5% sensitivity, evidence is provided, that OCT can discern the subtle differences between benign and malignant-potential tissue types, at a level of accuracy approaching that required for *leave-in-situ* management of colorectal polyps.

These preliminary but promising results underscore the potential impact of the proposed approach in advancing early cancer detection and prevention. With future developments, this method can offer significant improvements in the accuracy of endoscopic OCT imaging and its application in colon polyp management and may have significant implications for the early diagnosis and management of CRC. If a tool is successfully developed, it could offer guidance for managing CRC as well as enable crucial new research that will ultimately improve patient prognosis and quality of life. Furthermore, that application of feature-enhanced deep learning with decision-level fusion could be applied to other OCT image classification challenges where the microstructure alone does not provide adequate information for an accurate diagnosis.

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